

Antibodies are a family of structurally complex proteins produced by cells of the immune system called B lymphocytes, to defend us against foreign invaders like bacteria and viruses. The population of B lymphocytes of each individual is able to produce a repertoire of antibodies that allows to recognize and bind up to 10^7 different targets (called antigens) of various shape and nature. Each antibody molecule is highly specific for a single antigen. After binding, the antibody contributes to antigen clearance. Each B lymphocyte produces antibodies with a single antigen specificity.

Antibodies structure

Antibodies, also known as immunoglobulins, have a characteristic Y-shape structure. Each antibody is made of 4 protein chains: two identical long or “heavy” chains (H), and two identical short or “light” chains (L). The antigen binding pocket (ABP) is formed by the pairing of a H with a L chain, so that each antibody has two identical ABP.

Antibodies in every day life

Therapeutic applications:

Treatment of various inflammatory and allergic diseases and cancer.

Passive immunity:

As post-exposure prophylaxis against various infections, monoclonal antibodies targeting specific antigens of the infecting organism can be administered. Examples include immunoglobulins against hepatitis B, rabies, and tetanus.

Diagnostic reagents:

Diagnostic kits employ various antibodies tagged with detection molecules, such as fluorescent dyes or enzymes, that permit to “visualize” the presence of a specific antigens in the clinical specimen.

Mono and polyclonal antibodies

Monoclonal antibodies are produced by a single B lymphocyte, thus all specific for a same antigen, all identical and all binding the same part of such antigen.

Polyclonal antibodies are produced by different B lymphocytes. They are all specific for a same antigen but bind at different parts of it.

